

The IT Operations Ontology (ITOPS) resource

Access at <https://github.com/IBM/ITOPS-ontology>

*R. Uceda-Sosa, N. Mihindukulasooriya, S. Bansal, S. Nagar, A. Kumar, V. Agarwal, Gaetano
Rossiello, A. Gliozzo*
IBM Research

Questions/comments: rosariou@us.ibm.com

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Introduction

We have built a domain-agnostic pipeline for domain-specific ontologies that leverages information on Wikidata, Wikipedia and DBpedia. Each of the three stages of the pipeline extends the previous ones by using a variety of symbolic and ML/DL techniques.

In this document we discuss the outcome of each stage and show sample SPARQL queries. We also discuss the content and topology of the GLO upper library of objects.

The product of each stage is a turtle (.ttl) file, ITOPS_S1.ttl, ITOPS_S2.ttl and ITOPS_S3.ttl, each extending the prior one. All of them build upon a General Library of Objects (GLO), which provides a general ontological framework to the domain specific graphs.

Positive concepts

- Algorithm
- Authentication
- Command
- Configuration file
- Computer
- Computer language
- Computer model
- ...

Negative concepts

- Album
- Computer File
- Data set
- Digital Media
- Request for Comments
- Video game
- ...

User Curated

Figure 1. The pipeline used to build ITOPS

Each of the provided files can be installed in a triplestore and inferencing engine that supports RDF/OWL (Blazegraph,Allegro,etc.)

CAVEAT -- It is worth noting that we've used a private installation of Wikidata using an RDF/OWL dump from late January, 2020, so there may be instances where our results differ from those in the live service.

The General Library of Objects

We have created a small, general T-Box describing domain entities (glo:DomainEntity), statements about these entities and a set of high-level relations among them. We have populated it with 74 general-purpose entities derived from Wikidata. These entities are instances of glo:DomainEntity and are mostly related by a partial order relation, glo:subConceptOf, which subsumes wdt:P279 (subclass of) and wdt:P31 (instance of). This is

done so that subsequent extensions to the ontology don't need to redraw the boundaries between T-Box and A-Box.

We call this T-Box plus the seed A-Box the General Library of Objects (GLO). A snapshot is depicted below.

Figure 2. GLO Upper Ontology

The GLO a shortcut for <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#> . In order to understand GLO's content better, let's look at a sample entity.

Figure 3. Sample entity using GLO vocabulary

Let's consider the entity "Metadata" in ITOPS, which uses the GLO. Each entity has metadata annotation properties associated to it, like aliases, comments, provenance (in this case indicating the step used to produce the entity) and external links (to Wikidata in this case). The

relation `glo:subConceptOf` indicates that `itops:Metadata` is both an `ITEntity` and `glo:Information`. We discuss below how the inheritance hierarchy is constructed.

The relation `itops:has_parts_of_the_class` is one of the relations induced from the domain. These are defined as `rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:domainEntityObjProp`. All relations in a GLO ontology are categorized depending on whether they related domain entities (`glo:domainEntityObjProp`), statements (`glo:statementConceptObjProp`) or link statements to the domain entities they reference (`glo:toReferentObjProp`). Notice that some of the objects are instances, while others are strings. This is due to the construction pipeline, which seeks to limit the subgraph to relevant entities and avoids dangling references by referring to entities outside the scope of the ontology by strings.

S1 – The file `ITOPS_S1.ttl`

This file defines the `itops` namespace (<http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>) and is generated from a list of 82 common concepts in the TechQA dataset (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.02984>).

wd:Q8366	algorithm	wd:Q42195763	data storage	wd:Q178648	peripheral device
wd:Q7397	All software	wd:Q175263	data structure	wd:Q82	printer
wd:Q212108	authentication	wd:Q8513	database	wd:Q1466064	processor
wd:Q1126190	CDC standard	wd:Q7126717	download	wd:Q9143	Programming Language
wd:Q218341	checksum	wd:Q1332193	error message	wd:Q188267	programming paradigm
wd:Q182656	chipset		exit status (for error code)	wd:Q962139	programming style
wd:Q483639	cloud computing	wd:Q2553232	filename extension	wd:Q179550	software bug
wd:Q29149990	coded character set	wd:Q186157	filesystem permissions	wd:Q4485156	software feature
wd:Q1079196	command	wd:Q1172314	hacker attack	wd:Q2165493	software pipeline
	communications protocol	wd:Q4494907	Hardware	wd:Q28777292	software problem
wd:Q132364	computer	wd:Q3966	input device	wd:Q20631656	software release
wd:Q68	computer architecture	wd:Q178648	installation (computer)	wd:Q220499	streaming media
wd:Q173212	computer key	wd:Q836862	interface standard	wd:Q28530532	type of software
wd:Q27884930	Computer language	wd:Q6046311	Internet Service Provider	wd:Q42253	uniform resource locator (computer)
wd:Q629206	computer model	wd:Q11371	internet standard	wd:Q1183329	unit of information
wd:Q55990535	computer model series	wd:Q290378	IRI	wd:Q3550873	upload
wd:Q60484681	computer network	wd:Q37071	keyword	wd:Q7126699	url redirection
wd:Q1301371	computer network protocol	wd:Q1072684	login	wd:Q1236807	user interface
wd:Q15836568	computer program	wd:Q472302	machine readable data	wd:Q47146	variable
wd:Q40056	computer user	wd:Q6723621	mask	wd:Q877977	variable -- categorical
wd:Q278368	computing	wd:Q591605	memory address	wd:Q2285707	variable -- ordinal
wd:Q179310	computing infrastructure	wd:Q835713	metadata	wd:Q7100785	web camera
	configuration file	wd:Q180160	mobile device	wd:Q29576	web conference
wd:Q15411548	control flow	wd:Q5082128	object oriented class	wd:Q1543677	wifi
wd:Q1571814	cpu design	wd:Q4479242	offline	wd:Q29643	digital media
wd:Q868299	data erasure	wd:Q2015967	online	wd:Q1076968	
wd:Q1303814	data format	wd:Q73368	online chat		
wd:Q574817	data set	wd:Q287198	password		
wd:Q494823		wd:Q161157			
wd:Q1172284					

Figure 4. Seed concepts for S1

From these seed terms we generate the relevant subgraph from Wikidata and brought as children of itops:. The top level entities are then ‘linked’ to the GLO ontology by following the wdt:P31 and wdt:P279 relations. In Figure 3, itops:Metadata is a subConcept of both itops:ITEntity and glo:Information. Notice that the intermediate concepts (those between the top layer of ITOPS and the lower layers of GLO) are ignored at this time.

It is worth noting that a population from these terms generates a large ontology with many useless hierarchies. In particular, music albums (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q482994>), videogames (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q7889>) or datasets (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q117284>) introduce thousands of instances with little use in the IT operations domain. After manually pruning some of the sections with an editor, we’ve compiled a list (DoNotPopulate) so subsequent runs do not include these instances. In the case of S1 the list is:

wd:Q482994	album
wd:Q354004	audio storage device
wd:Q149757	compact audio cassette
wd:Q66221	computer data storage
wd:Q82753	computer file
wd:Q7927908	computer game accessory
wd:Q1571814	configuration file
wd:Q494823	data format
wd:Q1172284	data set
wd:Q1076968	digital media
wd:Q2553232	exit status
wd:Q169930	extended play
wd:Q7020	genome
wd:Q17589470	home console
wd:Q6805426	mediawiki extension
wd:Q180160	metadata
wd:Q212971	request for comments
wd:Q877977	variable
wd:Q7889	video games
wd:Q171	wiki
wd:Q17442446	wikimedia internal element

Fig 5. DoNotPopulate() list

Because of this DoNotPopulate list, we call this process “Partial Forest” population. In the glo:provenanceKB of the items obtained like this, we include this term and a timestamp.

The outcome of this step is a file with 47374 entities and 220 domain entity relation (plus subConceptOf). In the last section we show a few sample queries to obtain topology information at the end of this document.

S2 – The file ITOPS_S2.ttl

The S2 version of ITOPS seeks to leverage the categories from the English Wikipedia. Most Wikipedia articles are manually labelled with tags corresponding to categories. Such tags can contain information that is not explicitly in Wikidata. Most entities in Wikidata can then be linked to their corresponding Wikipedia article through interwiki information. This allows us to get the associated Wikipedia categories for each Wikidata entity.

For instance, if we take an entity such as “computer keyboard” (Q250), the corresponding Wikipedia page is tagged with four categories “computer peripherals”, “computing input devices”, “flexible electronics”, and “game control methods”. While the first two are domain-specific categories containing mostly IT domain entities, the latter two are more generic. Thus, we need a method for distinguishing between those.

We have used metrics that indicate the heterogeneity of entities in a category and their overlap with the initial partial forest to identify domain-specific categories. For that, we extract all Wikipedia articles tagged with a given category and collect their corresponding entities along with their class types. For example, the entities “computer peripherals” are typed as instances of few classes that subclasses of “peripheral equipment” (Q178648) class while entities in “flexible electronics” are typed from many diverse classes that are far from each other in the class hierarchy. Furthermore, a large portion (75%) of entities in ‘computer peripherals’ overlap with the initial partial forest while for ‘flexible electronics’ it is around 9%.

The result is a file with 51096 entities and 220 domain entity relation (plus subConceptOf, of course). In the last section we show a few sample queries to obtain topology information at the end of this document.

S3 – The file ITOPS_S3.ttl

S2 does not take care of customization of ITOPS ontology with domain specific resources. IT domain has glossaries readily available for multiple sub-domains. These glossaries capture specialized knowledge of a domain and are usually a good quality data source.

S3 uses Deep Learning to classify concepts from glossaries along the glo:subConceptOf hierarchy in the ontology.

Four such glossaries are used:

1. https://www.ibm.com/support/knowledgecenter/STXNRM_3.14.7/coss.doc/
2. https://www.ibm.com/support/knowledgecenter/SSEPGG_11.1.0/com.ibm.db2.luw.glossary.doc/doc/glossary.html
3. <https://www.dpsolutions.com/success-center/it-terminology-glossary>
4. <https://flexsystem.lenovofiles.com/help>

Due to IP concerns, only the name and external link to the terms are stored in ITOPS_S3.

The result is a file with 53193 entities and 220 domain entity relation (plus subConceptOf, of course). In the last section we show a few sample queries to obtain topology information at the end of this document.

How to query ITOPS

These queries can be run either of the three files, as the three stages result in an ontology with the <<http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>> namespace. The examples provided here are from S1

QUERY: To obtain all properties in the graph (object, annotation, datatype)

```
prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>
prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?property ?propertyLabel WHERE {
  {
    ?property rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topObjectProperty .
  } UNION
  {
    ?property rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topDatatypeProperty .
  }
  UNION
  {
    ?property rdfs:subPropertyOf u2o:topAnnotationProperty .
  }
}
```

QUERY: To obtain data for a given entity – outgoing properties

We select only the children properties and entities

Name:

▼ Annotations

glo:WDLINK

glo:alias

glo:provenanceKB

rdfs:comment

rdfs:label

▼ Other Properties

glo:subConceptOf

has_parts_of_the_class

rdf:type

```

prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>
prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?propertyLabel ?entity ?entityLabel WHERE {
    itops:Metadata ?property ?entity .
    ?property rdfs:label ?propertyLabel .
    OPTIONAL {
        ?entity rdfs:label ?entityLabel .
    }
    # The most specific entity
    FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?otherEntity glo:subConceptOf ?entity .
        itops:Metadata ?property ?otherEntity .
    }
}

```

```

        FILTER (?otherEntity != ?entity)
    }
# The most specific property
FILTER NOT EXISTS {?otherProperty rdfs:subPropertyOf ?property.
    itops:Metadata ?otherProperty ?entity .
    FILTER (?otherProperty != ?property)
}
} ORDER BY ?propertyLabel

```

The results:

propertyLabel	entity	entityLabel
provenance KB	Partial Forest 20200521192455	
alias	metacontent	
has parts of the class	access	
has parts of the class	addressee	
has parts of the class	author	
has parts of the class	file size	
has parts of the class	matter	
has parts of the class	proprietor	
has parts of the class	situation	
has parts of the class	statistic	
has parts of the class	title	
has parts of the class	timestamp	
has parts of the class	<http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Data_type>	data type
has parts of the class	<http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Timestamp>	timestamp
subconcept of	<http://www.ibm.com/GLO#Information>	information
subconcept of	<http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#ITEntity>	IT Entity
wikidata link	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q180160	

QUERY: To obtain data for a given entity – incoming references
Using the same example from itops:Metadata

▼ Incoming References

← glo:subConceptOf ▼

- ◆ Annotation
- ◆ Archival_description
- ◆ Attribute
- ◆ Bibliographic_metadata
- ◆ Date
- ◆ Extremely_annotational_rdf_markup
- ◆ Geospatial_metadata
- ◆ Header
- ◆ Nif_2_dot_0
- ◆ Preservation_metadata
- ◆ Relation
- ◆ Standard_architecture_for_universal_comment_extensions
- ◆ Subject
- ◆ Tag
- ◆ Timestamp
- ◆ Web_annotation_data_model

← facet_of ▼

- ◆ Tag

← main_subject ▼

- ◆ Open_data_web

← use ▼

- ◆ Metadata_registry

The result:

propertyLabel	entity	entityLabel
facet of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Tag	tag
main subject	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Open_data_web	open data web
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Annotation	annotation
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Timestamp	timestamp
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Archival_description	archival description
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Attribute	attribute
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Bibliographic_metadata	bibliographic metadata
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Date	date
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Extremely_annotational_rdf_markup	extremely annotational rdf markup
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Geospatial_metadata	geospatial metadata
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Nif_2_dot_0	nif 2.0
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Header	header
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Tag	tag
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Preservation_metadata	preservation metadata
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Relation	relation
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Standard_architecture_for_universal_comment_extensions	standard architecture for universal comment extensions
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Subject	subject
subconcept of	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Web_annotation_data_model	web annotation data model
use	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Metadata_registry	metadata registry

QUERY: To obtain all entities in GLO namespace

prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>

prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?entity ?entityLabel WHERE {
    ?entity glo:subConceptOf glo:DomainEntity .
    FILTER(STRSTARTS(STR(?entity), "http://www.ibm.com/GLO#"))
    ?entity rdfs:label ?entityLabel .
} ORDER BY ?entity
```

QUERY: to count all statements in the graph

```
SELECT DISTINCT (COUNT(*) as ?triples) WHERE
    { ?s ?p ?o . }
```

QUERY: to count all statement minus those with metadata

prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>

prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>

```
SELECT DISTINCT (COUNT(*) as ?triples) WHERE {
    ?s ?p ?o .
    FILTER NOT EXISTS {
        ?p rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topAnnotationProperty .
        ?p rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topDataProperty .
        ?s rdfs:comment ?o .
        ?s rdfs:label ?o
    }
}
```

QUERY: to count all statement minus those with metadata

```
prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>
```

```
prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>
```

```
SELECT DISTINCT (COUNT(*) as ?triples) WHERE {  
  ?s ?p ?o .  
  FILTER NOT EXISTS {  
    ?p rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topAnnotationProperty .  
    ?p rdfs:subPropertyOf glo:topDataProperty .  
    ?s rdfs:comment ?o .  
    ?s rdfs:label ?o  
  }  
}
```

QUERY: programming languages associated to “Adobe”

```
prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>
```

```
prefix itops: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>
```

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?value ?valueLabel WHERE {  
  ?item glo:subConceptOf itops:Software .  
  { ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel.  
    FILTER (CONTAINS(LCASE(?itemLabel), "adobe")) .  
    OPTIONAL { ?item glo:alias ?alias }  
  }  
  UNION  
  {  
    ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel .  
    ?item glo:alias ?alias .  
    FILTER (CONTAINS(LCASE(?alias), "adobe")) .  
  }  
  ?item itops:programming_language ?value .  
  OPTIONAL { ?value rdfs:label ?valueLabel . }  
}
```

The result:

value	valueLabel
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#C	c
ActionScript	
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Adobe_air	adobe air
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Adobe_flash	adobe flash
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Apache_flex	apache flex
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#C_plus_plus	c++
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Hypertext_markup_language	hypertext markup language
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Java	java
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Cascading_style_sheets_2	cascading style sheets
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Lua	lua
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Object_pascal	object pascal
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Javascript	javascript
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Objective_c	objective_c
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Python	python

QUERY: Two hop graph (productive nodes)

Starting with itops:Laptop_model

prefix glo: <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#>

prefix ITOPS: <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#>

CONSTRUCT {

 ?x0 ?p0 ?x1 .

 ?x0 ?p1 ?x2 .

 ?x2 ?p2 ?x3 .

}

WHERE {

 VALUES ?x0SUP {

 <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Laptop_model>

 }

 VALUES ?x3SUP {

 <http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#ITEntity>

 }

 ?x0 glo:subConceptOf ?x0SUP .

? x3 glo:subConceptOf ?x3SUP .

 #Only domain properties

 ?p0 rdfs:subPropertyOf <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp> .

 FILTER (?p0 != <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp>).

 ?p1 rdfs:subPropertyOf <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp> .

```

FILTER (?p1 != <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp> ).
?p2 rdfs:subPropertyOf <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp> .
FILTER (?p2 != <http://www.ibm.com/GLO#domainEntityObjProp> ).
?x0 ?p0 ?x1 .
?x0 ?p1 ?x2 .
?x2 ?p2 ?x3 .
}

```

The results:

subject	predicate	object
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Surface_laptop	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#developer	Microsoft
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Surface_laptop	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#operating_system	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Windows_10_s
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Windows_10_s	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#follows	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Windows_rt
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Surface_laptop	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#followed_by	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Surface_laptop_2
http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#Surface_laptop	http://www.ibm.com/ITOPS#official_website	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/surface/devices/surface-laptop/